

What is depth. What is breadth. Define probability. Define measure.

question: does making something beautiful release dopamine? That could explain learning. Does dopamine help learn more quickly? I know it related to goal-seeking behavior.

prediction vs. association. Question: how much of prediction is about association? if you weaken association, do you get more causal effects? region 1 is related to region 2, and these regions are very specific -> causality. We ask causal questions for concepts we're already familiar with anyway.

define beyond reasonable doubt? how much truth before brain perceives statement as truth?

one implication: causal questions are strictly about neural activity, and they assume one directional neural activity. How do you get one-directional neural activity? Activation of region 1 makes region 2 more likely to activate, but not the other way around?

Prediction: this phenomenon happens in brain. That it is often region 1 that makes region 2 more likely to activate, but not the other way around.

Mechanism prediction 1: region 1 is larger than region 2. Both are connected.

important: this knowledge is time-sensitive, as humans are changing and adapting very quickly right now because of the fast flow of information.

how does asking "why" affect this? How do you ask why and get this one sided neural activity encoded? Is this about humans learning a sequence? I would say so. It's just humans learning things explicitly. This is not implicit.

Challenge: do I separate quantum phenomenon from this? quantum bundles thing vs computation. Are we using this as a strict model?

Ok. Let's start with a big graph. then do all of this.

define computation then. That's important. it should not be about if and else statements. Those are completely unnecessary. Computation is not necessarily discrete.

Define number then. define operation. define measure. define truth.

Ok. Found it. I just need a continuous model of computation. Then each node is activated with a certain probability when you measure. How do you avoid time here? I don't want markov chain. and I want some reinforcement mechanism. All of this has to be through wiring.

define flow. Define electricity. Define motion.

can each measurement change state without time? Don't think that's right way. Each assumes time.

How to do that? Have another probabilistic model record data.

"as long as one part reacts more to cue, and activates other neurons, you have time."

But that assumes cue. Avoid that.

define measurement. I can just explain the computation model with another computation model that stores data of the first in a way I can access and verify with my time indexing.

ok. We're taking measure from classical world.

Then, we find time as emergent. Which gives cause as emergent. Which gives computation as emergent.



2 objects on left. 2 objects on right. Objects on left have larger measure than objects on right.

All objects are assigned probability.

We can measure objects and see left objects' "effect", since each time we measure objects on right, which from our view is affected by measure 1, we see it has gotten bigger.

But from that's classical view. I want measures to reinforce themselves.

define motion. That's important. Define flow.

define more. define measure in this framework itself. Then you're good. 1 has bigger measure than 2 and so on...

connections of left objects are more "recognizable" from each other? measures both get larger.

each time we measure objects on right, we see objects on right have gotten bigger.

I need a reinforcement operator.

as long as two objects are dissimilar enough, but not too dissimilar, they're close, and one is bigger than other. This gives time.

ok. we have issues now. I'm using neural activity as inspiration for all of this. and neural activity itself is measured by time.

ok. Objects with larger measure come before.

also, activate multiple parts. that's still vague. give electricity, is what I'm thinking. but electricity is related to time again.

excitation = more. how do you get excitation of multiple things? that's issue now. I'm thinking probability of activity "goes" higher. But "goes" again assumes time of course. Measure of both objects increase size. If I measure right objects first time, and then second time, their measures have gone up.